

List of Fishes of the Galapagos Archipelago, Ecuador

JACK STEIN GROVE

Galapagos Education & Research Alliance

University of Pennsylvania, 3803 Locust Walk, Philadelphia, PA 19104, USA

 <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7110-2931> E-mail: grovejack509@gmail.com

DOUGLAS J. LONG

Curator of Natural History, Museum of Riverside, 3580 Mission Inn Ave., Riverside, CA 92501, USA

*Research Associate, Department of Ichthyology, California Academy of Sciences,
55 Music Concourse Dr., San Francisco, CA 94118, USA*

 <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6816-8040> E-mail: dlong@calacademy.org

D. ROSS ROBERTSON

Smithsonian Tropical Research Institute, Balboa, Panama

 <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3972-149X> E-mail: RobertsonDR@si.edu

BENJAMIN C. VICTOR

Ocean Science Foundation, 4051 Glenwood, Irvine, CA 92604, USA

Guy Harvey Research Institute, Nova Southeastern University, 8000 North Ocean Drive, Dania Beach, FL 33004, USA

 <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8728-9585> E-mail: ben@coralreeffish.com

In preparation for the IUCN Redlist Assessment for the fishes of the Galapagos Archipelago, we have reviewed the literature to date and surveyed the observations of the various experts and naturalists most familiar with the region. Using this information, we have assembled a list of fishes known to occur on the islands (Table 1). We define the area as the islands and adjoining shelf slope to the abyssal region, and evaluate whether each species comprises a resident population or is a vagrant (likely not to be a self-recruiting population). We consider species that are limited to the islands as endemics, notwithstanding vagrant reports at adjacent areas (e.g. the well-known red-lipped batfish *Ogcocephalus darwini*).

The listing is a continuing project and the database of accumulated records, evidence, citations, information, and justifications will be regularly archived now and in future at the Zenodo archive (www.zenodo.org). The data are an accumulation and critical evaluation of published literature, as well as online sources of museum records (www.vertnet.org; www.fishnet2.org; Eschmeyer's Catalog of Fishes at www.researcharchive.calacademy.org/research/ichthyology/catalog/fishcatmain.asp), databases of museum and observational records (www.fishbase.net; www.obis.org; SFTEP Shorefishes of the Tropical Eastern Pacific at www.biogeodb.stri.si.edu/caribbean/en/pages), databases of DNA-sequence records (www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov; www.boldsystems.org), and online sources of photographic evidence, such as www.inaturalist.org and a variety of commercial photography platforms.

The present list, arranged in taxonomic order following Catalog of Fishes, includes 644 species of fishes, with 56 in Chondrichthyes and 576 bony fishes. Of the total, 66 are considered vagrants, many of which are Indo-Pacific coral-reef species that are sporadic or even single records. There are 37 documented endemic species, including some reef species with relatively short larval lives, such as blennioids, gobioids, and haemulids.

Citation: Grove, J.S., Long, D.J., Robertson, D.R. & Victor, B.C. (2022) List of Fishes of the Galapagos Archipelago, Ecuador. *Journal of the Ocean Science Foundation*, 39, 14–22.

doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7065587>

TABLE 1

Fishes of the Galapagos Archipelago

Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic	Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic
<i>Eptatretus goslnei</i>	Myxinidae	R	<i>Echinorhinus cookei</i>	Echinorhinidae	R
<i>Eptatretus grouseri</i>	Myxinidae	R	<i>Tetronarce tremens</i>	Torpedinidae	R
<i>Eptatretus mccoskeri</i>	Myxinidae	R	<i>Pseudobatos planiceps</i>	Rhinobatidae	R
<i>Eptatretus bobwisneri</i>	Myxinidae	R	<i>Rajella eisenhardti</i>	Rajidae	R
<i>Myxine greggi</i>	Myxinidae	R	<i>Rostroraja velezi</i>	Rajidae	R
<i>Myxine phantasma</i>	Myxinidae	R	<i>Bathyraja abyssicola</i>	Arhynchobatidae	R
<i>Myxine martini</i>	Myxinidae	R	<i>Bathyraja peruana</i>	Arhynchobatidae	R
<i>Rubicundus lakeside</i>	Myxinidae	R	<i>Bathyraja richardsoni</i>	Arhynchobatidae	R
<i>Hexanchus griseus</i>	Hexanchidae	R	<i>Bathyraja spinosissima</i>	Arhynchobatidae	R
<i>Notorynchus cepedianus</i>	Hexanchidae	R	<i>Gurgesiella furvescens</i>	Gurgesiellidae	R
<i>Heterodontus quoyi</i>	Heterodontidae	R	<i>Hypanus dipterurus</i>	Dasyatidae	R
<i>Rhincodon typus</i>	Rhincodontidae	R	<i>Hypanus longus</i>	Dasyatidae	R
<i>Odontaspis ferox</i>	Odontaspidae	R	<i>Pteroplatytrygon violacea</i>	Dasyatidae	R
<i>Alopias pelagicus</i>	Alopiidae	R	<i>Taeniurops meyeri</i>	Dasyatidae	R
<i>Alopias superciliosus</i>	Alopiidae	R	<i>Styracura pacifica</i>	Potamotrygonidae	R
<i>Isurus oxyrinchus</i>	Lamnidae	R	<i>Aetobatus laticeps</i>	Aetobatidae	R
<i>Bythaelurus giddingsi</i>	Scyliorhinidae	R	<i>Aetomylaeus asperrimus</i>	Myliobatidae	R
<i>Apristurus kampae</i>	Pentanchidae	R	<i>Myliobatis peruvianus</i>	Myliobatidae	R
<i>Apristurus</i> n. sp.	Pentanchidae	R	<i>Rhinoptera steindachneri</i>	Rhinopteridae	R
<i>Galeus</i> n. sp.	Pentanchidae	R	<i>Mobula birostris</i>	Mobulidae	R
<i>Mustelus albipinnis</i>	Triakidae	R	<i>Mobula mobular</i>	Mobulidae	R
<i>Mustelus mento</i>	Triakidae	R	<i>Mobula munkiana</i>	Mobulidae	R
<i>Triakis maculata</i>	Triakidae	R	<i>Mobula tarapacana</i>	Mobulidae	R
<i>Carcharhinus albimarginatus</i>	Carcharhinidae	R	<i>Mobula thurstoni</i>	Mobulidae	V
<i>Carcharhinus altimus</i>	Carcharhinidae	R	<i>Chimaera</i> sp.	Chimaeridae	R
<i>Carcharhinus amblyrhynchos</i>	Carcharhinidae	V	<i>Hydrolagus alphas</i>	Chimaeridae	R
<i>Carcharhinus falciformis</i>	Carcharhinidae	R	<i>Hydrolagus mccoskeri</i>	Chimaeridae	R
<i>Carcharhinus galapagensis</i>	Carcharhinidae	R	<i>Hydrolagus</i> sp.	Chimaeridae	R
<i>Carcharhinus limbatus</i>	Carcharhinidae	R	<i>Elops affinis</i>	Elopidae	V
<i>Carcharhinus longimanus</i>	Carcharhinidae	R	<i>Albula esuncula</i>	Albulidae	V
<i>Nasolamia velox</i>	Carcharhinidae	R	<i>Halosaurus attenuatus</i>	Halosauridae	R
<i>Prionace glauca</i>	Carcharhinidae	R	<i>Myroconger nigrodentatus</i>	Myrocongridae	R
<i>Triaenodon obesus</i>	Carcharhinidae	R	<i>Anarchias galapagensis</i>	Muraenidae	R
<i>Galeocerdo cuvier</i>	Galeocerdonidae	R	<i>Echidna nebulosa</i>	Muraenidae	R
<i>Sphyrna lewini</i>	Sphyrnidae	R	<i>Echidna nocturna</i>	Muraenidae	R
<i>Sphyrna mokarran</i>	Sphyrnidae	R	<i>Enchelycore lichenosa</i>	Muraenidae	R
<i>Sphyrna tiburo</i>	Sphyrnidae	R	<i>Enchelycore octaviana</i>	Muraenidae	R
<i>Sphyrna zygaena</i>	Sphyrnidae	R	<i>Gymnomuraena zebra</i>	Muraenidae	R
<i>Isistius brasiliensis</i>	Dalatiidae	R	<i>Gymnothorax angusticeps</i>	Muraenidae	R
<i>Centroscyllium nigrum</i>	Etmopteridae	R	<i>Gymnothorax buroensis</i>	Muraenidae	R
<i>Centrophorus squamosus</i>	Centrophoridae	R	<i>Gymnothorax castaneus</i>	Muraenidae	R

TABLE 1 cont.

Fishes of the Galapagos Archipelago

Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic	Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic
<i>Gymnothorax dovii</i>	Muraenidae	R	<i>Anchoa ischana</i>	Engraulidae	R
<i>Gymnothorax flavimarginatus</i>	Muraenidae	V	<i>Cetengraulis mysticetus</i>	Engraulidae	V
<i>Gymnothorax javanicus</i>	Muraenidae	V	<i>Engraulis ringens</i>	Engraulidae	R
<i>Gymnothorax meleagris</i>	Muraenidae	V	<i>Harengula thrissina</i>	Clupeidae	R
<i>Gymnothorax panamensis</i>	Muraenidae	R	<i>Lile stolifera</i>	Clupeidae	R
<i>Gymnothorax pictus</i>	Muraenidae	V	<i>Opisthonema berlangai</i>	Clupeidae	RE
<i>Gymnothorax undulatus</i>	Muraenidae	V	<i>Opisthonema libertate</i>	Clupeidae	R
<i>Muraena argus</i>	Muraenidae	R	<i>Etrumeus acuminatus</i>	Dussumieriidae	R
<i>Muraena clepsydra</i>	Muraenidae	R	<i>Sardinops sagax</i>	Alosidae	R
<i>Muraena lentiginosa</i>	Muraenidae	R	<i>Bathytroctes microlepis</i>	Alepocephalidae	R
<i>Scuticaria tigrina</i>	Muraenidae	V	<i>Einara macrolepis</i>	Alepocephalidae	R
<i>Uropterygius macrocephalus</i>	Muraenidae	R	<i>Narcetes erimelas</i>	Alepocephalidae	R
<i>Uropterygius polystictus</i>	Muraenidae	R	<i>Photostylus pycnopterus</i>	Alepocephalidae	R
<i>Uropterygius versutus</i>	Muraenidae	R	<i>Holtbyrnia latifrons</i>	Platyroctidae	R
<i>Chlopsis bicollaris</i>	Chlopsidae	R	<i>Maulisia isaacsi</i>	Platyroctidae	R
<i>Apterichthys equatorialis</i>	Ophichthidae	R	<i>Platyroctes apus</i>	Platyroctidae	R
<i>Callechelys galapagensis</i>	Ophichthidae	RE	<i>Chanos chanos</i>	Chanidae	R
<i>Herpetoichthys fossatus</i>	Ophichthidae	R	<i>Argentina aliceeae</i>	Argentinidae	R
<i>Ichthyapus selachops</i>	Ophichthidae	R	<i>Bathylagoides nigrigenys</i>	Bathylagidae	R
<i>Myrichthys xysturus</i>	Ophichthidae	R	<i>Cyclothone acclinidens</i>	Gonostomatidae	R
<i>Ophichthus arneutes</i>	Ophichthidae	RE	<i>Cyclothone atraria</i>	Gonostomatidae	R
<i>Ophichthus rugifer</i>	Ophichthidae	R	<i>Cyclothone obscura</i>	Gonostomatidae	R
<i>Paraetharchus opercularis</i>	Ophichthidae	R	<i>Cyclothone pallida</i>	Gonostomatidae	R
<i>Phaenomonas pinnata</i>	Ophichthidae	V	<i>Cyclothone signata</i>	Gonostomatidae	R
<i>Quassiremus evionthas</i>	Ophichthidae	R	<i>Argyropelecus aculeatus</i>	Sternoptychidae	R
<i>Scytalichthys miurus</i>	Ophichthidae	V	<i>Argyropelecus affinis</i>	Sternoptychidae	R
<i>Facciolella equatorialis</i>	Nettastomatidae	R	<i>Argyropelecus lychnus</i>	Sternoptychidae	R
<i>Ariosoma gilberti</i>	Congridae	V	<i>Argyropelecus olfersii</i>	Sternoptychidae	R
<i>Bathycongrus</i> n. sp.	Congridae	R	<i>Argyropelecus sladeni</i>	Sternoptychidae	R
<i>Bathycongrus varidens</i>	Congridae	R	<i>Maurolicus amethystinopunctatus</i>	Sternoptychidae	R
<i>Chiloconger dentatus</i>	Congridae	V	<i>Sternoptyx diaphana</i>	Sternoptychidae	R
<i>Gnathophis cinctus</i>	Congridae	V	<i>Sternoptyx obscura</i>	Sternoptychidae	R
<i>Heteroconger klausewitzi</i>	Congridae	R	<i>Ichthyococcus irregularis</i>	Phosichthyidae	R
<i>Japonoconger</i> n. sp.	Congridae	R	<i>Vinciguerria lucetia</i>	Phosichthyidae	R
<i>Japonoconger proriger</i>	Congridae	R	<i>Vinciguerria poweriae</i>	Phosichthyidae	R
<i>Paraconger californiensis</i>	Congridae	R	<i>Astronesthes boulengeri</i>	Stomiidae	R
<i>Paraconger similis</i>	Congridae	R	<i>Astronesthes martensii</i>	Stomiidae	R
<i>Xenomystax atrarius</i>	Congridae	R	<i>Bathophilus filifer</i>	Stomiidae	R
<i>Anguilla marmorata</i>	Anguillidae	R	<i>Malacosteus niger</i>	Stomiidae	R
<i>Anchoa argentivittata</i>	Engraulidae	R	<i>Stomias atriventer</i>	Stomiidae	R

TABLE 1 cont.

Fishes of the Galapagos Archipelago

Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic	Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic
<i>Stomias boa</i>	Stomiidae	R	<i>Triphoturus oculum</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Stomias colubrinus</i>	Stomiidae	R	<i>Stylephorus chordatus</i>	Stylephoridae	R
<i>Guentherus altivela</i>	Ateleopodidae	R	<i>Bregmaceros bathymaster</i>	Bregmacerotidae	R
<i>Aulopus bajacali</i>	Aulopidae	R	<i>Bregmaceros macclellandi</i>	Bregmacerotidae	R
<i>Chlorophthalmus mento</i>	Chlorophthalmidae	R	<i>Merluccius gayi</i>	Merlucciidae	R
<i>Bathypterois atricolor</i>	Ipnopidae	R	<i>Trachyrincus helolepis</i>	Trachyrincidae	R
<i>Bathypterois pectinatus</i>	Ipnopidae	R	<i>Antimora rostrata</i>	Moridae	R
<i>Ipnops agassizii</i>	Ipnopidae	R	<i>Gadella filifer</i>	Moridae	R
<i>Scopelarchoides nicholsi</i>	Scopelarchidae	R	<i>Gadella thysthlon</i>	Moridae	R
<i>Scopelarchus guentheri</i>	Scopelarchidae	R	<i>Laemonema gracillipes</i>	Moridae	R
<i>Scopelosaurus hubbsi</i>	Notosudidae	R	<i>Physiculus nematopus</i>	Moridae	R
<i>Synodus lacertinus</i>	Synodontidae	R	<i>Coelorinchus canus</i>	Macrouridae	R
<i>Synodus scituliceps</i>	Synodontidae	R	<i>Coryphaenoides anguliceps</i>	Macrouridae	R
<i>Synodus sechurae</i>	Synodontidae	R	<i>Coryphaenoides armatus</i>	Macrouridae	R
<i>Lestidiops pacificum</i>	Paralepididae	R	<i>Coryphaenoides boops</i>	Macrouridae	R
<i>Evermannella ahlstromi</i>	Evermannellidae	R	<i>Coryphaenoides bucephalus</i>	Macrouridae	R
<i>Scopelengys tristris</i>	Neoscopelidae	R	<i>Coryphaenoides bulbiceps</i>	Macrouridae	R
<i>Bolinichthys longipes</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Coryphaenoides delsolari</i>	Macrouridae	R
<i>Diaphus pacificus</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Coryphaenoides gypsochilus</i>	Macrouridae	R
<i>Diaphus rafenesquii</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Coryphaenoides myersi</i>	Macrouridae	R
<i>Diaphus termophilus</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Mataeocephalus tenuicauda</i>	Macrouridae	R
<i>Diaphus theta</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Nezumia convergens</i>	Macrouridae	R
<i>Diogenichthys laternatus</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Nezumia loricata</i>	Macrouridae	R
<i>Gonichthys tenuiculus</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Nezumia stelgidolepis</i>	Macrouridae	R
<i>Gonichthys venetus</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Nezumia ventralis</i>	Macrouridae	R
<i>Hygophum reinhardti</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Scopelogadus mizolepis</i>	Melamphaidae	R
<i>Lampanyctus hubbsi</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Hoplostethus pacificus</i>	Trachichthyidae	R
<i>Lampanyctus idostigma</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Zu cristatus</i>	Trachipteridae	R
<i>Lampanyctus macropterus</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Myripristis berndti</i>	Holocentridae	R
<i>Lampanyctus omostigma</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Myripristis leiognathus</i>	Holocentridae	R
<i>Lampanyctus parvicauda</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Neoniphon suborbitalis</i>	Holocentridae	R
<i>Lampanyctus resplendens</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Brotula ordwayi</i>	Ophidiidae	R
<i>Lampanyctus ritteri</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Cataetx sp. vs simus</i>	Ophidiidae	R
<i>Lampanyctus tenuiformis</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Dicrolene nigra</i>	Ophidiidae	R
<i>Myctophum aurolaternatum</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Eretmichthys pinnatus</i>	Ophidiidae	R
<i>Myctophum nitidulum</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Lepohidium pardale</i>	Ophidiidae	R
<i>Notolychnus valdiviae</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Monomitopus malispinosus</i>	Ophidiidae	R
<i>Symbolophorus evermanni</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Ophidion sp. A</i>	Ophidiidae	R
<i>Symbolophorus reversus</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Otophidium indefatigabile</i>	Ophidiidae	R
<i>Triphoturus mexicanus</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Carapus mourlani</i>	Carapidae	R

TABLE 1 cont.

Fishes of the Galapagos Archipelago

Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic	Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic
<i>Echiodon exsilium</i>	Carapidae	R	<i>Lepidopus manis</i>	Trichiuridae	R
<i>Encheliophis vermicularis</i>	Carapidae	R	<i>Trichiurus lepturus</i>	Trichiuridae	R
<i>Calamopteryx jeb</i>	Bythitidae	RE	<i>Mulloidichthys dentatus</i>	Mullidae	R
<i>Diplacanthopoma jordani</i>	Bythitidae	R	<i>Pseudupeneus grandisquamis</i>	Mullidae	R
<i>Grammonus diagrammus</i>	Bythitidae	R	<i>Synchiropus atrilabiatus</i>	Callionymidae	R
<i>Lucifuga inopinata</i>	Bythitidae	R	<i>Aulostomus chinensis</i>	Aulostomidae	R
<i>Petrotyx hopkinsi</i>	Bythitidae	R	<i>Fistularia commersonii</i>	Fistulariidae	R
<i>Pseudonus acutus</i>	Bythitidae	R	<i>Fistularia corneta</i>	Fistulariidae	R
<i>Ogilbia deroyi</i>	Dinematichthyidae	RE	<i>Bryx veleronis</i>	Syngnathidae	R
<i>Ogilbia galapagosensis</i>	Dinematichthyidae	RE	<i>Cosmocampus arctus</i>	Syngnathidae	R
<i>Porichthys margaritatus</i>	Batrachoididae	R	<i>Doryrhamphus excisus</i>	Syngnathidae	R
<i>Seriolaella violacea</i>	Centrolophidae	R	<i>Hippocampus ingens</i>	Syngnathidae	R
<i>Cubiceps pauciradiatus</i>	Nomeidae	R	<i>Apogon atradorsatus</i>	Apogonidae	R
<i>Nomeus gronovii</i>	Nomeidae	R	<i>Apogon dovii</i>	Apogonidae	R
<i>Psenes arafurensis</i>	Nomeidae	R	<i>Apogon pacificus</i>	Apogonidae	R
<i>Psenes cyanophrys</i>	Nomeidae	R	<i>Dormitator latifrons</i>	Eleotridae	V
<i>Psenes pellucidus</i>	Nomeidae	R	<i>Eleotris picta</i>	Eleotridae	V
<i>Psenes sio</i>	Nomeidae	R	<i>Gobiomorus maculatus</i>	Eleotridae	V
<i>Peprilus medius</i>	Stromateidae	R	<i>Bathygobius lineatus</i>	Gobiidae	R
<i>Chiasmodon niger</i>	Chiasmodontidae	R	<i>Bollmannia macropoma</i>	Gobiidae	R
<i>Chiasmodon subniger</i>	Chiasmodontidae	R	<i>Chriolepis tagus</i>	Gobiidae	RE
<i>Acanthocybium solandri</i>	Scombridae	R	<i>Clarkichthys bilineatus</i>	Gobiidae	R
<i>Auxis rochei</i>	Scombridae	R	<i>Coryphopterus urospilus</i>	Gobiidae	R
<i>Auxis thazard</i>	Scombridae	R	<i>Eleotrica cableae</i>	Gobiidae	RE
<i>Euthynnus lineatus</i>	Scombridae	R	<i>Lythrypnus gilberti</i>	Gobiidae	RE
<i>Katsuwonus pelamis</i>	Scombridae	R	<i>Lythrypnus rhizophora</i>	Gobiidae	R
<i>Sarda orientalis</i>	Scombridae	R	<i>Microdesmus dipus</i>	Gobiidae	R
<i>Scomber japonicus</i>	Scombridae	R	<i>Tigrigobius nesiotes</i>	Gobiidae	R
<i>Scomberomorus sierra</i>	Scombridae	R	<i>Schindleria praematura</i>	Schindleriidae	R
<i>Thunnus alalunga</i>	Scombridae	R	<i>Centropomus viridis</i>	Centropomidae	R
<i>Thunnus albacares</i>	Scombridae	R	<i>Sphyraena barracuda</i>	Sphyraenidae	V
<i>Thunnus obesus</i>	Scombridae	R	<i>Sphyraena helleri</i>	Sphyraenidae	V
<i>Brama dussumieri</i>	Bramidae	R	<i>Sphyraena idiaestes</i>	Sphyraenidae	R
<i>Taractes rubescens</i>	Bramidae	R	<i>Citharichthys darwini</i>	Cyclopsettidae	RE
<i>Gempylus serpens</i>	Gempylidae	R	<i>Citharichthys gnathus</i>	Cyclopsettidae	R
<i>Lepidocybium flavobrunneum</i>	Gempylidae	R	<i>Syacium latifrons</i>	Cyclopsettidae	V
<i>Nealotus tripes</i>	Gempylidae	R	<i>Syacium maculiferum</i>	Cyclopsettidae	V
<i>Ruvettus pretiosus</i>	Gempylidae	R	<i>Bothus leopardinus</i>	Bothidae	R
<i>Aphanopus intermedius</i>	Trichiuridae	R	<i>Bothus mancus</i>	Bothidae	R
<i>Benthodesmus tenuis</i>	Trichiuridae	R	<i>Monolene maculipinna</i>	Bothidae	R

TABLE 1 cont.

Fishes of the Galapagos Archipelago

Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic	Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic
<i>Hippoglossina bollmani</i>	Paralichthyidae	R	<i>Echeneis naucrates</i>	Echeneidae	R
<i>Paralichthys woolmani</i>	Paralichthyidae	R	<i>Phtheichthys lineatus</i>	Echeneidae	R
<i>Trinectes fonsecensis</i>	Achiridae	V	<i>Remora albescens</i>	Echeneidae	R
<i>Aseraggodes herrei</i>	Soleidae	R	<i>Remora australis</i>	Echeneidae	R
<i>Symphurus atramentatus</i>	Cynoglossidae	R	<i>Remora brachyptera</i>	Echeneidae	R
<i>Symphurus diabolicus</i>	Cynoglossidae	R	<i>Remora osteochir</i>	Echeneidae	R
<i>Symphurus varius</i>	Cynoglossidae	R	<i>Remora remora</i>	Echeneidae	R
<i>Nematistius pectoralis</i>	Nematistiidae	R	<i>Coryphaena equiselis</i>	Coryphaenidae	R
<i>Xiphias gladius</i>	Xiphiidae	R	<i>Coryphaena hippurus</i>	Coryphaenidae	R
<i>Istiompax indica</i>	Istiophoridae	R	<i>Opistognathus galapagensis</i>	Opistognathidae	R
<i>Istiophorus platypterus</i>	Istiophoridae	R	<i>Abudefduf concolor</i>	Pomacentridae	R
<i>Kajikia audax</i>	Istiophoridae	R	<i>Abudefduf troschelii</i>	Pomacentridae	R
<i>Makaira nigricans</i>	Istiophoridae	R	<i>Azurina atrilobata</i>	Pomacentridae	R
<i>Tetrapturus angustirostris</i>	Istiophoridae	R	<i>Azurina eupalama</i>	Pomacentridae	RE
<i>Alectis ciliaris</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Azurina intercrusma</i>	Pomacentridae	V
<i>Caranx caballus</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Chromis alta</i>	Pomacentridae	R
<i>Caranx caninus</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Microspathodon bairdii</i>	Pomacentridae	R
<i>Caranx ignobilis</i>	Carangidae	V	<i>Microspathodon dorsalis</i>	Pomacentridae	R
<i>Caranx lugubris</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Nexilosus latifrons</i>	Pomacentridae	R
<i>Caranx melampygius</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Stegastes acapulcoensis</i>	Pomacentridae	R
<i>Caranx sexfasciatus</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Stegastes arcifrons</i>	Pomacentridae	R
<i>Decapterus macrosoma</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Stegastes beebei</i>	Pomacentridae	R
<i>Decapterus muroadsi</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Stegastes flavilatus</i>	Pomacentridae	R
<i>Elagatis bipinnulata</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Atherinella nesiotis</i>	Atherinopsidae	R
<i>Euprepocaranx dorsalis</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Melanorhinus cyanelus</i>	Atherinopsidae	R
<i>Ferdauia orthogrammus</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Cololabis adocetus</i>	Scomberesocidae	R
<i>Gnathanodon speciosus</i>	Carangidae	V	<i>Ablennes hians</i>	Belonidae	R
<i>Naucrates ductor</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Platybelone argalus</i>	Belonidae	R
<i>Oligoplites saurus</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Strongylura exilis</i>	Belonidae	R
<i>Selar crumenophthalmus</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Tylosurus fodiator</i>	Belonidae	R
<i>Selene peruviana</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Tylosurus pacificus</i>	Belonidae	R
<i>Seriola lalandi</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Euleptorhamphus viridis</i>	Hemiramphidae	R
<i>Seriola peruana</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Hemiramphus saltator</i>	Hemiramphidae	R
<i>Seriola rivoliana</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Hyporhamphus gilli</i>	Hemiramphidae	V
<i>Trachinotus kennedyi</i>	Carangidae	V	<i>Hyporhamphus naos</i>	Hemiramphidae	R
<i>Trachinotus paitensis</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Oxyporhamphus micropterus</i>	Hemiramphidae	R
<i>Trachinotus rhodopus</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Cheilopogon atrisignis</i>	Exocoetidae	R
<i>Trachinotus stilbe</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Cheilopogon dorsomacula</i>	Exocoetidae	R
<i>Trachurus murphyi</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Cheilopogon spilonotopterus</i>	Exocoetidae	R
<i>Uraspis helvola</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Cheilopogon xenopterus</i>	Exocoetidae	R

TABLE 1 cont.

Fishes of the Galapagos Archipelago

Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic	Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic
<i>Cypselurus angusticeps</i>	Exocoetidae	V	<i>Heteropriacanthus carolinus</i>	Priacanthidae	R
<i>Cypselurus callopterus</i>	Exocoetidae	R	<i>Pristigenys serrula</i>	Priacanthidae	R
<i>Exocoetus monocirrhus</i>	Exocoetidae	R	<i>Malacanthus brevirostris</i>	Malacanthidae	R
<i>Exocoetus volitans</i>	Exocoetidae	R	<i>Caulolatilus affinis</i>	Latilidae	R
<i>Fodiator rostratus</i>	Exocoetidae	R	<i>Caulolatilus princeps</i>	Latilidae	R
<i>Hirundichthys marginatus</i>	Exocoetidae	R	<i>Hoplopagrus guentherii</i>	Lutjanidae	R
<i>Hirundichthys rondeletii</i>	Exocoetidae	R	<i>Lutjanus aratus</i>	Lutjanidae	R
<i>Hirundichthys speculiger</i>	Exocoetidae	R	<i>Lutjanus argentiventris</i>	Lutjanidae	R
<i>Parexocoetus brachypterus</i>	Exocoetidae	V	<i>Lutjanus guttatus</i>	Lutjanidae	R
<i>Prognichthys sealei</i>	Exocoetidae	R	<i>Lutjanus inermis</i>	Lutjanidae	R
<i>Prognichthys tringa</i>	Exocoetidae	R	<i>Lutjanus jordani</i>	Lutjanidae	R
<i>Chaenomugil proboscideus</i>	Mugilidae	R	<i>Lutjanus novemfasciatus</i>	Lutjanidae	R
<i>Dajaus monticola</i>	Mugilidae	R	<i>Lutjanus viridis</i>	Lutjanidae	R
<i>Mugil galapagensis</i>	Mugilidae	RE	<i>Pristipomoides zonatus</i>	Lutjanidae	V
<i>Mugil thoburni</i>	Mugilidae	RE	<i>Diapterus brevirostris</i>	Gerreidae	R
<i>Arcos poecilophthalmos</i>	Gobiesocidae	R	<i>Eucinostomus currani</i>	Gerreidae	R
<i>Tomicodon chilensis</i>	Gobiesocidae	R	<i>Eucinostomus dowii</i>	Gerreidae	R
<i>Tomicodon petersii</i>	Gobiesocidae	R	<i>Eucinostomus gracilis</i>	Gerreidae	R
<i>Lepidonectes corallicola</i>	Triptyerygiidae	RE	<i>Eugerres lineatus</i>	Gerreidae	R
<i>Cottoclinus canops</i>	Labrisomidae	RE	<i>Gerres simillimus</i>	Gerreidae	R
<i>Dialommus fuscus</i>	Labrisomidae	R	<i>Anisotremus espinozai</i>	Haemulidae	R
<i>Gobioclinus dendriticus</i>	Labrisomidae	R	<i>Brachygenys jessiae</i>	Haemulidae	RE
<i>Labrisomus jenkinsi</i>	Labrisomidae	RE	<i>Genyatremus scapularis</i>	Haemulidae	R
<i>Labrisomus multiporosus</i>	Labrisomidae	R	<i>Haemulon maculicauda</i>	Haemulidae	R
<i>Malaccoctenus tetranemus</i>	Labrisomidae	R	<i>Haemulon scudderii</i>	Haemulidae	R
<i>Malaccoctenus zonogaster</i>	Labrisomidae	RE	<i>Haemulon sexfasciatum</i>	Haemulidae	R
<i>Starksia galapagensis</i>	Labrisomidae	RE	<i>Microlepidotus lethopristis</i>	Haemulidae	RE
<i>Acanthemblemaria castroi</i>	Chaenopsidae	RE	<i>Orthopristis cantharinus</i>	Haemulidae	R
<i>Chaenopsis schmitti</i>	Chaenopsidae	RE	<i>Orthopristis chalceus</i>	Haemulidae	R
<i>Ekemblemaria</i> sp.	Chaenopsidae	RE	<i>Orthopristis forbesi</i>	Haemulidae	RE
<i>Dactyloscopus lacteus</i>	Dactyloscopidae	R	<i>Rhencus macracanthus</i>	Haemulidae	V
<i>Gillellus semicinctus</i>	Dactyloscopidae	R	<i>Xenichthys agassizii</i>	Haemulidae	RE
<i>Myxodagnus sagitta</i>	Dactyloscopidae	RE	<i>Xenichthys xanti</i>	Haemulidae	R
<i>Platygillellus rubellulus</i>	Dactyloscopidae	RE	<i>Archosargus pourtalesii</i>	Sparidae	RE
<i>Entomacrodus chiostictus</i>	Blenniidae	R	<i>Calamus brachysomus</i>	Sparidae	R
<i>Hypsoblennius brevipinnis</i>	Blenniidae	R	<i>Calamus taurinus</i>	Sparidae	R
<i>Ophioblennius steindachneri</i>	Blenniidae	R	<i>Cilus gilberti</i>	Sciaenidae	R
<i>Plagiotremus azaleus</i>	Blenniidae	R	<i>Corvula macrops</i>	Sciaenidae	R
<i>Hemilutjanus macrophthalmos</i>	Hemilutjanidae	R	<i>Cynoscion phoxocephalus</i>	Sciaenidae	R
<i>Cookeolus japonicus</i>	Priacanthidae	V	<i>Larimus pacificus</i>	Sciaenidae	R

TABLE 1 cont.

Fishes of the Galapagos Archipelago

Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic	Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic
<i>Odontoscion eurymesops</i>	Sciaenidae	R	<i>Iniistius pavo</i>	Labridae	R
<i>Pareques perissa</i>	Sciaenidae	RE	<i>Nicholsina denticulata</i>	Labridae-Scarinae	R
<i>Umbrina galapagorum</i>	Sciaenidae	R	<i>Novaculichthys taeniourus</i>	Labridae	R
<i>Alphestes immaculatus</i>	Serranidae	R	<i>Sagittalarya inornata</i>	Labridae	R
<i>Anthias noeli</i>	Serranidae	R	<i>Scarus compressus</i>	Labridae-Scarinae	R
<i>Cephalopholis panamensis</i>	Serranidae	R	<i>Scarus ghobban</i>	Labridae-Scarinae	R
<i>Cratinus agassizii</i>	Serranidae	R	<i>Scarus perrico</i>	Labridae-Scarinae	R
<i>Dermatolepis dermatolepis</i>	Serranidae	R	<i>Scarus rubroviolaceus</i>	Labridae-Scarinae	R
<i>Diplectrum eumelum</i>	Serranidae	V	<i>Semicossyphus darwini</i>	Labridae	R
<i>Diplectrum macropoma</i>	Serranidae	V	<i>Stethojulis bandanensis</i>	Labridae	R
<i>Epinephelus analogus</i>	Serranidae	R	<i>Thalassoma grammaticum</i>	Labridae	R
<i>Epinephelus colonus</i>	Serranidae	R	<i>Thalassoma lucasanum</i>	Labridae	R
<i>Epinephelus labriformis</i>	Serranidae	R	<i>Thalassoma purpureum</i>	Labridae	R
<i>Hemanthias peruanus</i>	Serranidae	V	<i>Xyrichtys victori</i>	Labridae	R
<i>Hyporthodus cifuentesi</i>	Serranidae	R	<i>Lycodapus australis</i>	Zoarcidae	R
<i>Hyporthodus mystacinus</i>	Serranidae	R	<i>Melanostigma bathium</i>	Zoarcidae	R
<i>Hyporthodus niphobles</i>	Serranidae	R	<i>Thermarces cerberus</i>	Zoarcidae	R
<i>Liopropoma fasciatum</i>	Serranidae	R	<i>Ammodytoides gilli</i>	Ammodytidae	R
<i>Liopropoma longilepis</i>	Serranidae	R	<i>Kathetostoma averruncus</i>	Uranoscopidae	V
<i>Mycteroperca olfax</i>	Serranidae	R	<i>Bellator farrago</i>	Triglidae	R
<i>Mycteroperca xenarcha</i>	Serranidae	V	<i>Peristedion barbiger</i>	Triglidae	V
<i>Paralabrax albomaculatus</i>	Serranidae	RE	<i>Peristedion crustosum</i>	Triglidae	R
<i>Paralabrax humeralis</i>	Serranidae	R	<i>Prionotus miles</i>	Triglidae	RE
<i>Pronotogrammus multifasciatus</i>	Serranidae	R	<i>Prionotus stephanophrys</i>	Triglidae	R
<i>Pseudogramma thaumasia</i>	Serranidae	R	<i>Ectreposebastes imus</i>	Scorpaenidae	R
<i>Rypticus bicolor</i>	Serranidae	R	<i>Idiastion hageyi</i>	Scorpaenidae	R
<i>Rypticus nigripinnis</i>	Serranidae	R	<i>Phenacoscorpius mccoskeri</i>	Scorpaenidae	R
<i>Serranus aequidens</i>	Serranidae	R	<i>Pontinus clemensi</i>	Scorpaenidae	R
<i>Serranus psittacinus</i>	Serranidae	R	<i>Pontinus</i> sp. A	Scorpaenidae	R
<i>Serranus stilbostigma</i>	Serranidae	RE	<i>Pontinus</i> sp. B	Scorpaenidae	R
<i>Bodianus diplotaenia</i>	Labridae	R	<i>Pontinus</i> sp. C	Scorpaenidae	R
<i>Bodianus eclancheri</i>	Labridae	R	<i>Pontinus strigatus</i>	Scorpaenidae	R
<i>Calotomus carolinus</i>	Labridae-Scarinae	R	<i>Pontinus vaughani</i>	Scorpaenidae	R
<i>Decodon melasma</i>	Labridae	R	<i>Scorpaena cocosensis</i>	Scorpaenidae	R
<i>Halichoeres adustus</i>	Labridae	V	<i>Scorpaena histrio</i>	Scorpaenidae	R
<i>Halichoeres chierchiae</i>	Labridae	R	<i>Scorpaena mystes</i>	Scorpaenidae	R
<i>Halichoeres dispilus</i>	Labridae	R	<i>Scorpaena wellingtoni</i>	Scorpaenidae	RE
<i>Halichoeres melanotis</i>	Labridae	V	<i>Scorpaenodes rubrivinctus</i>	Scorpaenidae	R
<i>Halichoeres nicholsi</i>	Labridae	R	<i>Scorpaenodes xyris</i>	Scorpaenidae	R
<i>Halichoeres notospilus</i>	Labridae	R	<i>Taenianotus triacanthus</i>	Scorpaenidae	V

TABLE 1 cont.

Fishes of the Galapagos Archipelago

Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic	Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic
<i>Trachyscorpia osheri</i>	Sebastidae	R	<i>Ogcocephalus darwini</i>	Ogcocephalidae	RE
<i>Paraliparis darwini</i>	Liparidae	R	<i>Abantennarius coccineus</i>	Antennariidae	R
<i>Paraliparis galapagoensis</i>	Liparidae	R	<i>Abantennarius sanguineus</i>	Antennariidae	R
<i>Kuhlia mugil</i>	Kuhliidae	R	<i>Antennarius commerson</i>	Antennariidae	V
<i>Oplegnathus insignis</i>	Oplegnathidae	R	<i>Antennatus strigatus</i>	Antennariidae	R
<i>Kyphosus elegans</i>	Kyphosidae	R	<i>Fowlerichthys avalonis</i>	Antennariidae	R
<i>Kyphosus ocyurus</i>	Kyphosidae	R	<i>Melanocetus murrayi</i>	Melanocetidae	R
<i>Kyphosus vaigiensis</i>	Kyphosidae	R	<i>Chaenophryne draco</i>	Oneirodidae	R
<i>Girella freminvillii</i>	Girellidae	RE	<i>Microlophichthys microlophus</i>	Oneirodidae	R
<i>Cirrhitichthys oxycephalus</i>	Cirrhitidae	R	<i>Cryptopsaras couseii</i>	Ceratiidae	R
<i>Cirrhitus rivulatus</i>	Cirrhitidae	R	<i>Masturus lanceolatus</i>	Molidae	R
<i>Oxycirrhites typus</i>	Cirrhitidae	R	<i>Mola alexandrini</i>	Molidae	V
<i>Epigonus merleni</i>	Epigonidae	R	<i>Mola mola</i>	Molidae	R
<i>Howella pammelas</i>	Howellidae	R	<i>Ranzania laevis</i>	Molidae	R
<i>Holacanthus passer</i>	Pomacanthidae	R	<i>Chilomycterus reticulatus</i>	Diodontidae	R
<i>Pomacanthus zonipectus</i>	Pomacanthidae	V	<i>Cylichthys spilostylus</i>	Diodontidae	V
<i>Chaetodon auriga</i>	Chaetodontidae	V	<i>Diodon eydouxi</i>	Diodontidae	R
<i>Chaetodon humeralis</i>	Chaetodontidae	R	<i>Diodon holacanthus</i>	Diodontidae	R
<i>Chaetodon kleinii</i>	Chaetodontidae	V	<i>Diodon hystrix</i>	Diodontidae	R
<i>Chaetodon lunula</i>	Chaetodontidae	V	<i>Arothron hispidus</i>	Tetraodontidae	R
<i>Chaetodon meyeri</i>	Chaetodontidae	V	<i>Arothron meleagris</i>	Tetraodontidae	R
<i>Chaetodon unimaculatus</i>	Chaetodontidae	V	<i>Arothron nigropunctatus</i>	Tetraodontidae	V
<i>Forcipiger flavissimus</i>	Chaetodontidae	R	<i>Canthigaster amboinensis</i>	Tetraodontidae	V
<i>Johnrandallia nigrirostris</i>	Chaetodontidae	R	<i>Canthigaster janthinoptera</i>	Tetraodontidae	V
<i>Prognathodes carlhubbsi</i>	Chaetodontidae	R	<i>Canthigaster punctatissima</i>	Tetraodontidae	R
<i>Luvarus imperialis</i>	Luvaridae	R	<i>Canthigaster valentini</i>	Tetraodontidae	V
<i>Zanclus cornutus</i>	Zanclidae	R	<i>Lagocephalus lagocephalus</i>	Tetraodontidae	R
<i>Acanthurus mata</i>	Acanthuridae	V	<i>Sphoeroides angusticeps</i>	Tetraodontidae	R
<i>Acanthurus nigricans</i>	Acanthuridae	R	<i>Sphoeroides annulatus</i>	Tetraodontidae	R
<i>Acanthurus triostegus</i>	Acanthuridae	R	<i>Sphoeroides lobatus</i>	Tetraodontidae	R
<i>Acanthurus xanthopterus</i>	Acanthuridae	R	<i>Ostracion meleagris</i>	Ostraciidae	R
<i>Naso annulatus</i>	Acanthuridae	V	<i>Aluterus scriptus</i>	Monacanthidae	R
<i>Naso brevirostris</i>	Acanthuridae	V	<i>Cantherhines dumerilii</i>	Monacanthidae	V
<i>Naso vlamingii</i>	Acanthuridae	V	<i>Balistes polylepis</i>	Balistidae	R
<i>Prionurus laticlavus</i>	Acanthuridae	R	<i>Canthidermis maculata</i>	Balistidae	R
<i>Lophiodes spilurus</i>	Lophiidae	R	<i>Melichthys niger</i>	Balistidae	R
<i>Dibranchius cracens</i>	Ogcocephalidae	RE	<i>Melichthys vidua</i>	Balistidae	V
<i>Dibranchius discors</i>	Ogcocephalidae	RE	<i>Pseudobalistes naufragium</i>	Balistidae	R
<i>Dibranchius erinaceus</i>	Ogcocephalidae	R	<i>Sufflamen verres</i>	Balistidae	R
<i>Dibranchius hystrix</i>	Ogcocephalidae	R	<i>Xanthichthys caeruleolineatus</i>	Balistidae	V
<i>Halieutopsis tumifrons</i>	Ogcocephalidae	R	<i>Xanthichthys mento</i>	Balistidae	R